

Evaluation of Attention Deficit Related to Digital Addiction in Early Childhood: Teachers' Perspectives

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Abstract: The early childhood period, often referred to as the “magical years of life” by many scientists, is when development occurs most rapidly after the prenatal stage. This rapid development necessitates heightened attention to ensure that children spend their time in ways that promote healthy growth. It is frequently observed that technological devices have become an integral part of children’s daily lives, with children interacting with these devices throughout the day. This has prompted researchers to examine children’s use of digital technologies from various perspectives. The purpose of this study is to investigate attention deficit related to digital addiction in early childhood through the perspectives of teachers. To achieve this, a qualitative case study using semi-structured interviews was conducted, and the data were analyzed using content analysis. The study was conducted during the spring term of the 2023–2024 academic year. The findings reveal that 20 preschool teachers, aged between 45 and 55, participated in the study. Most participants held undergraduate degrees, had over 15 years of professional experience, and were employed in preschool education institutions.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Okul öncesi dönem
Okul öncesi eğitim
Dijital bağımlılık
Dikkat eksikliği
Öğretmen bakış açısı

Okul Öncesi Dönemde Dijital Bağımlılığa Bağlı Dikkat Eksikliği Konusunun Değerlendirilmesi: Öğretmen Görüşleri

Özet: Çoğu bilim insanı tarafından yaşamın sihirli yılları olarak belirtilen erken çocukluk dönemi, gelişimin doğum öncesinden sonra en hızlı olduğu dönemdir. Gelişimin hızlı olması, çocukların sağlıklı gelişimi için zamanlarını kaliteli geçirmeleri konusunda daha dikkatli olmamızı gerekli kılmaktadır. Teknolojik aletlerin çocukların da günlük yaşamlarının parçası haline geldiği ve çocukların bu teknolojik aletlerle gün içerisinde etkileşime geçtikleri sıkça gözlemlenmektedir. Bu da araştırmacıları çocukların dijital teknolojileri kullanımı konusunu çeşitli boyutlarıyla ele alan araştırmalar yapmaya sevk etmektedir. Bu araştırmada; okul öncesi dönemde dijital bağımlılığa bağlı dikkat eksikliği konusunun öğretmen görüşlerine göre incelenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Bu amaca yönelik araştırmada, yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme tekniği ile yapılan nitel verilere dayalı bir durum çalışması yapılmış, içerik analizi yöntemi ile analiz edilmiştir. Araştırma 2023- 2024 eğitim öğretim yılı bahar döneminde uygulanmıştır. Araştırmadan elde edilen sonuçlar incelendiğinde, araştırmaya 20 okul öncesi öğretmenin katıldığı, çoğunluğunun 45 ile 55 yaş arasında olan bireylerden oluştuğu görülmektedir. Katılımcıların çoğunluğunun lisans mezunu olduğu, mesleki deneyiminin 15 yılın üzerinde olan ve okul öncesi kurumlarında çalışan sınıf öğretmenlerinden oluştuğu görülmüştür.

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1. Introduction

The preschool period holds significant importance in a person's lifespan. This stage is marked by rapid development, encompasses critical developmental phases, and serves as a foundational period for shaping a child's behaviors (Trawick-Smith, 2013). It is also crucial for personality development (Oktay, 1999; Tuncer & Zelyurt, 2023). For these reasons, how children spend their time and the influence of those in their immediate environment during early childhood are of great importance. Early childhood spans from birth to around eight years, during which children undergo substantial developmental milestones across various domains. Numerous studies emphasize the importance of supporting children's development appropriately and effectively during this period (Tunçeli & Zembat, 2017).

Reaching the optimal developmental potential of children requires providing suitable opportunities from the moment they are born. Education, which should ideally begin even before birth, significantly influences a child's development through the family, physical, and social environment. The preschool and early primary school years are critical for children's growth (Oktay, 1999). What is given—or not given—during early childhood significantly shapes their future. Children's time with technological devices at home or in their social environment profoundly impacts their health and development. According to Zembat (1992), the preschool period is when efforts are made in collaboration with families to develop children holistically from birth to the start of primary school. Cooperation with families is essential to foster positive physical, emotional, social, and mental development and support confidence and positive personality traits. Excessive time spent on technological devices—such as hours of television viewing, prolonged gaming on tablets or computers, or unmonitored use of smartphones—has increasingly been recognized as detrimental to children's social, cognitive, and emotional development (Tüzün, 2002).

Addiction, as a concept, can be both material and behavioral. Studies reveal diverse definitions of addiction. Seferoğlu and Yıldız (2013) define it as the state in which an individual feels temporarily good due to prolonged use of a substance, product, or service. Koçak et al. (2015) describe it as a compulsion to engage in harmful behaviors despite physical, social, or psychological detriments. Based on these definitions, digital addiction can be understood as excessive and prolonged use of digital devices. The prevalence of technological and digital addiction has evolved with advancements in technology, manifesting as internet addiction (Başköy, 2013; Gençer, 2011; Günüş, 2009), computer game addiction (Bilgin, 2015; Veltri et al., 2014), and digital addiction (Çukurkurulöz, 2016). The widespread accessibility of digital devices has made them an integral part of daily life for adults and children, lowering the use age to infancy (Alicamen, 2023; Arıkan & Zorba, 2019; Genç & Köksal, 2021; Nevski & Siibak, 2016; Sitepu et al., 2024). Research highlights challenges in managing children's screen time and regulating the content they consume (Akçay & Emiroğlu, 2016; Kars, 2010). Integrating digital devices into daily life reduces children's time on outdoor activities, leading to adverse effects. Excessive screen time has been linked to a decline in peer interaction and an increase in solitary play (Rosen et al., 2014).

Parents, teachers, and experts express concerns about children spending unregulated and extensive time on digital devices. Studies suggest that prolonged exposure to such devices can lead to addiction, which in turn results in adverse outcomes such as attention deficits (Nevski & Siibak, 2016; Yalçın-Irmak & Erdoğan, 2016). Attention deficit is one of the most commonly observed conditions in childhood. It often co-occurs with hyperactivity disorder, characterized by difficulties maintaining attention, impulsive behavior, and hyperactivity. These issues affect

interpersonal relationships and hinder academic success and social functioning (Dang et al., 2007). A review of the literature reveals a significant increase in research on digital addiction and attention deficits during the preschool period in 2020. However, no doctoral dissertations addressing this topic between 2012 and 2023 were identified. This study employs qualitative descriptive content analysis to examine the attention deficit caused by digital addiction in the preschool period from the teachers' perspective. The research seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the socio-demographic characteristics of the participating teachers?
2. What meanings do teachers attribute to the concept of digital addiction in preschool children?
3. What are the teachers' views on attention deficit in preschool children?
4. What are the teachers' perspectives on behaviors related to attention deficit due to digital addiction in preschool children?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

Based on teachers' perspectives, this study was designed as a qualitative research study to identify and elaborate on the issue of attention deficit due to digital addiction during the preschool period. The case study method was employed. Among the case study designs, the holistic single-case design was utilized. In holistic single-case designs, the situation is perceived as a single, comprehensive unit of analysis (Yin, 2009; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). This design is employed in three scenarios: first, when there is a well-formulated theory that needs to be confirmed or refuted; second, in cases that do not adhere to general standards but are extraordinarily unique and distinct; and third, in situations that no one has previously studied or accessed.

2.2. Participants

This study followed a purposeful sampling method to ensure practicality and accessibility. Twenty preschool teachers, most of whom were female, participated in the study. Based on teachers' perspectives, the study aimed to evaluate the attention deficit caused by digital addiction during preschool. The findings obtained from the preschool teachers' views are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variables	Categories	f	
Age	18-25	1	
	26-35	6	
	36-45	6	
	46-55	7	
Education Level	Undergraduate	16	
	Master's	4	
Experience (Years)	1-3	2	
	4-5	1	
	6-10	2	
	11-15	3	
	16-25	5	
Preschool Institution	26-30	2	
	Classroom Teachers	12	
	Subject Teachers	English	3
		Creative Arts	2
Play and Movement		1	

Music	1
Special Education	1

2.3. Data collection

The researcher used a semi-structured interview form with the participant teachers. Open-ended questions were created after a comprehensive review of the relevant literature to create the interview form. The interview form was sent to people who were experts in their field, and some feedback was provided by performing relevant tests. This feedback was used to create the interview form. The participants were called by phone before the interview, and a brief explanation of the study was given. It was also stated that the interview form would be applied voluntarily at the schools they worked at a time convenient for them. The interviews lasted 25 minutes, and the participants' responses to the questions were recorded, read, and confirmed.

2.4. Procedure

This study was conducted using a semi-structured interview form prepared by the researchers. Necessary permissions were obtained from the Ministry of Education and Culture to implement the interview form. Structured questions, pre-determined in advance, were used to collect data (Cohen et al., 2018). While preparing the interview form, care was taken to ensure the questions were clear, easy to understand, and structured to encourage detailed answers and facilitate effective communication with the participants. Efforts were made to avoid creating an excessive cognitive load for the interviewees by keeping the questions straightforward. Additionally, alternative questions and prompts were prepared to address cases where the respondents might not fully understand a question (Cohen et al., 2018).

The semi-structured interview form was reviewed by three field experts and developed based on a literature review. The interview form included questions specifically aimed at investigating the issue of attention deficit caused by digital addiction during the preschool period and consisted of eight questions. Face-to-face or telephone interviews were conducted with the participating teachers, and the researchers transcribed the qualitative data obtained to prevent data loss and analyzed using the content analysis method. The transcribed data were examined, and each dimension was assigned a number, resulting in a detailed transcription of the interviews. After transcription, the data obtained from participants were divided into meaningful segments, and these segments, which formed meaningful wholes within themselves, were named and coded. Once all the data were coded, a code list was created to serve as a reference for the analysis and organization of the data.

The researchers read the coding keys and interview transcriptions separately, and any areas of agreement or disagreement were discussed and adjusted accordingly. The reliability formula suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994) was applied to ensure reliability. The reliability of the study was calculated as 92% for the first question, 100% for the second question, and 96% on average. A reliability score above 70% is acceptable for research purposes (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Based on these results, the study was deemed reliable. Codes that showed consistency in the researchers' evaluations were organized according to themes, and the data were structured based on codes and themes.

2.5. Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using the descriptive analysis technique. The purpose of descriptive analysis is to transform raw data into a comprehensible and usable format for readers. The

data are summarized and interpreted in descriptive analysis based on pre-determined themes. Direct quotations are frequently included to reflect the interviewees or observed individuals' views vividly.

3. Findings

The themes derived from the participants' views were tabulated along with frequency distributions and interpreted.

Table 2.
Factors Affecting Attention in Preschool Children

Theme	Participant Opinions	f
Technology use (TV, tablet, phone)	P1, P2, P7, P8, P10, P11, P13, P14, P15, P16, P19	11
Educational materials	P3, P4, P5, P9, P11, P18, P19, P20	8
Family influence	P2, P5, P7, P8, P14, P15	6
Environmental factors (noise, classroom environment)	P1, P2, P3, P6, P9, P16, P17, P20	8
Type of activity	P4, P9, P11, P19	4
Learning style	P3, P9	2
Emotional state	P6, P7	2
Physical health (general health, sleep, nutrition)	P6, P7, P8, P9, P15, P16	6
Social relationships (peer relationships, group dynamics)	P6, P12	2
Teacher interaction (ability to capture attention)	P9	1

Table 2 indicates that teachers perceived technology use as having a significant impact on children's attention. The influence of educational materials, environmental factors, family dynamics, and physical health follows this.

- P3: *Visual stimuli in the classroom are among the factors that affect children's attention. Learning style varies depending on the student's profile.*
- P5: *Materials used in the classroom are not auditory or visual.*
- P6: *Among the factors affecting children's attention are conditions such as noise, temperature, and light, in addition to the presence of their peers nearby.*
- P7: *When children are ill, their attention tends to be scattered. If they come to school upset, they cannot concentrate on the lesson. If a child has a problem, they find it difficult to focus their attention.*
- P9: *Inadequate lesson stimuli in the classroom, the lack of appropriate educational materials, and the teacher's method of introducing the topic can impact attention. More visually engaging materials might capture their focus.*
- P11: *Activities such as using a musical instrument during a music lesson can attract students' interest. The absence of such elements can make it difficult for them to maintain focus.*
- P12: *The constant desire of preschool children to move impacts group dynamics and disrupts their focus.*
- P15: *Excessive use of tablets and phones can tire children, lead to sleep deprivation, and cause them to stay up late at night.*

Table 3.
Adverse Effects of Digital Devices

Theme	Participant Opinion	f
Adverse effects of digital devices	Yes	20
	No	0

Table 3 reveals that all participants believe digital devices adversely affect children's attention. The following quotations from the participants' remarks and responses vividly underpin the findings in the table.

- P5: *Digital devices can lead to effects such as introversion, difficulties in socializing, inability to communicate, irritability, and being prone to anger.*
- P6: *They may have physical effects on children (e.g., vision problems, posture disorders), and as a result of what they watch, negative psychological and emotional impacts are also possible.*
- P14: *Yes. Excessive use of phones can hinder the development of fine motor skills in children, negatively affect language development, and cause harm in physical, bodily, and mental aspects. They may also develop fears.*
- P17: *Of course. A child's sleep pattern and eye health can be disrupted. Their physical activities and social skills may decrease. They might lose the ability to sustain attention and concentrate, which negatively affects their success. Additionally, their mental health may deteriorate, increasing the risk of anxiety and depression.*

Table 4.
Digital Addiction

Theme	Participant Opinion	f
Continuous usage	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P8, P11, P12, P13, P17, P18, P19, P20	14
Weakening of social relationships	P1, P2, P16, P18	4
Misuse	P2, P9	2
Self-isolation	P9, P10, P14	3
Behavioral changes (irritable, aggressive)	P2	1
Reluctance to stop (loss of control)	P3, P7, P8, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, P17, P19	11
Disruption in age-appropriate activities	P5, P7, P8, P10, P14, P16, P18	7
Health problems (physical, psychological)	P6	1
Dependency on a digital device	P15, P16, P18	3
Behavioral changes	P6	1

Table 4 indicates that the majority of participants believe digital addiction is continuous and persistent. This view is followed by a reluctance to stop/lose control and behavioral changes, as exemplified in the following quotations from the participants' responses.

- P1: *The child constantly wants to play with technological devices, does not want to go outside, does not want to play with friends, and shuts down communication.*
- P2: *The child is using digital devices for long periods and not using them correctly.*
- P6: *Digital addiction is the intense use of digital devices throughout the day, to the extent that it threatens a person's physical and mental health."*
- P7: *Never put down the phone or tablet to the point of losing the desire to do anything else.*
- P10: *The child wants to look at the phone constantly, cannot detach from it, and does not want to do anything else.*
- P14: *The child completely disconnects from the world and sees themselves as one with digital devices. They lose communication with the outside world and never want to let go of the device, even eating while watching.*
- P16: *Not knowing how to act when digital devices are unavailable, not being able to wait, and digital devices hindering children's social skills, sleep, and nutrition needs.*

Table 5.

Challenges and problematic behaviors observed in children developing digital addiction

Theme	Category	Participant Opinions	f
Observed Challenges	Shyness in peer relationships	P1, P8, P17	3
	Difficulty in communication	P1, P2, P6	3
	Attention deficit	P6, P9, P13, P14, P17	5
	Social skills	P6, P10, P11, P12, P16	5
	Falling behind in studies	P7	1
	Decline in academic performance	P8	1
	Health problems	P9	1
	Inability to focus	P15, P17	2
	Inability to join peer relationships	P1, P11, P18	3
	Irritability	P2, P5, P11	3
	Anger issues	P14	1
	Desire to spend time alone	P5	1
	Lack of interest	P9, P14	2
	Selfishness, jealousy	P12	1
	Inability to understand instructions	P8, P13	2
Observed Problematic Behaviours	Drowsiness	P9, P15, P17	3
	Lack of play skills	P10	1
	Disobedience to commands and instructions	P6	1
	Living in a virtual world	P13, P14, P15, P18, P19, P20	6
	Use of profanity	P12, P18	2
	Bullying	P8, P12, P13, P14, P18	5
	Language development issues	P11	1
	Inability to share	P10	1
	Making mistakes in studies	P8	1
	Not listening to lessons, lack of interest	P6, P13, P18, P19	4
	Short attention span	P18	1
	Incompatibility	P5, P11	2
	Aggressive, violent behavior	P2, P6, P8, P11, P12, P13	6
	Mimicking what they see with friends	P14	1
	Desire to stay home and use digital devices	P18	1
Hyperactivity	P3, P11	2	
Perception problems	P13	1	
Inability to concentrate	P3, P6, P17	3	

Table 5 reveals that children experiencing digital addiction primarily encounter challenges related to attention deficits and difficulties in social skills. Furthermore, according to the collected opinions, the most frequently observed problematic behaviors include excessive immersion in virtual environments, aggressive or violent tendencies, bullying, and a lack of attentiveness or interest in academic lessons.

P1: *They behave shyly when it comes to playing with friends. They struggle with communication.*

P7: *Such children can fall behind in their lessons. However, among those who use digital devices in a controlled way and engage with educational programs, I have observed students acquiring knowledge in many areas and performing well in mathematics. However, they lag in writing skills.*

P8: *Their academic performance declines. They struggle to understand what is said, fail to complete their assignments correctly, and become isolated. They also face problems with friends and sometimes turn to violence or bullying.*

P11: *They experience language and speech disorders, are overly active, aggressive, irritable, and face social challenges. They do not know how to integrate into a group.*

P13: *Students with digital addiction are disinterested in lessons and experience difficulties in understanding. They fail to grasp the questions asked and have short attention spans. It is as if they*

live in another world. Moreover, they engage in peer bullying and exhibit violent behavior towards friends.

P14: It is challenging to draw the child back to their environment. They are constantly in a daze and influenced by the digital characters they see. They try to mimic what they see with their friends, distract others, and sometimes bully or frighten them. They engage in behaviors that put themselves in danger. Due to weak fine motor skills, they cannot participate in scissor activities or hold a pencil correctly. At home, they throw tantrums to get the phone.

P18: Students experiencing digital addiction have short attention spans. They are disinterested in classroom activities and constantly talk about the games they play or the videos they watch. They dislike group games and participating in activities. They dislike school and prefer going home to watch videos on their phones. They want to eat their meals while watching television. In the classroom, they become quiet while watching TV, but when it is turned off, they get angry at me. It becomes challenging to capture and sustain their attention during school activities. If these devices are taken away, they become irritable. Monitoring the content they are exposed to on digital devices is challenging. When exposed to inappropriate content for their age or developmental stage, they learn incorrect behaviors or use inappropriate words daily.

P20: Some children act dreamily. Some cannot differentiate between reality and the digital world. There are even those who perceive the digital world as accurate.

Table 6.
Solution Proposals

Theme	Participant Opinions	f
Limiting usage time	P1, P2, P4, P5, P6, P7, P9, P14, P15, P16, P17, P18	12
Parental education	P1, P3, P6, P8, P10, P11, P17, P18, P19	9
Communication/cooperation with family	P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P13, P14, P16, P19	14
Suggesting activities	P3, P4, P9, P10, P15, P20	6
Age-appropriate programs	P7, P9, P18	3
Informing the child	P8, P9, P17, P18	4
Parents should not play with devices.	P10, P17	2
Seeking expert support	P11, P13, P14, P19	4
Reward and punishment	P13, P16, P19	3
Removing the device completely	P16	1
Assigning responsibility	P12	1
Quality time activities with family	P14, P18	2
Encouraging play with peers	P12, P18, P20	3

Table 6 shows that participants recommend solutions such as fostering communication and collaboration with families, imposing limits on digital device usage, and providing parental education. The following quotes best exemplify these findings.

P4: I would talk to the family and recommend setting a time limit for digital device use. I would suggest directing the child towards different social activities.

P7: I consulted with the family to ensure that appropriate programs are shown under family supervision and for a limited time without compromising.

P6: I have tried to talk with the family, restrict the child's access to the digital environment, and educate families.

P12: I divide children into groups, encourage them to participate in games, and assign tasks and responsibilities.

P14: I contact the family. I recommend imposing limits. I tell them to be firm by showing the set time. I suggest families play with their children and spend quality time together.

P18: *I provide information to families, educating them about digital addiction and the problems it causes. I recommend controlling the time spent on devices and the content they are exposed to. In the classroom, I try to select activities that capture their interest. I inform children about digital devices and encourage them to spend time with friends.*

P19: *I collaborated with a special education teacher for my student with digital addiction. When the students did not mention a digital character, I rewarded them. We worked to distance them from this issue. I spoke with the family alongside my fellow teacher, and we worked together. Training sessions were conducted on what to do and how to communicate with the child.*

Table 7.
Opinions on Parental Education

Theme	Participant Opinions	f
Very beneficial and effective	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, P16, P17, P18, P19, P20	20
The MoNE should organize it.	P1, P3, P6, P7, P8, P14, P16	7
Each school should organize its own	P1, P3, P4, P6, P7, P8, P11, P16	8
Separate groups by age	P1, P3, P8, P17	4
Informative brochures	P3	1
Book recommendations	P4	1
Should start from September	P8, P14	2
Special meetings and training based on the child's needs	P9	1
Local authorities (e.g., municipalities) should organize	P11, P19	2
TV programs should be organized.	P11	1
Experts should conduct training.	P12, P14, P15	3
Training should be free.	P19	1
Training should be continuous.	P19	1
Examples of quality time activities should be taught	P13, P20	2
The parent-teacher association should organize it.	P14	1

Table 7 shows that most participants think parental education is beneficial and effective. This view is followed by suggestions that each school should organize its program and that MoNE should take responsibility.

P3: *Yes, seminars can be prepared in schools. The ministry can also organize these seminars. Informative brochures can be sent to families.*

P4: *Yes, it should be done. Schools should organize training sessions and provide families with recommendations. Additionally, book recommendations can be given.*

P8: *MoNE should prepare family education programs suitable for all school levels. Starting in September, each school should implement these programs within its structure.*

P15: *Yes. Experts should conduct training on topics like usage duration. Families should also be trained on programs suitable for children's age and educational support.*

P17: *It is necessary. Training should be divided by age groups, and families should receive awareness training with a solution-focused approach.*

Table 8 reveals that participants identify parental lack of knowledge, the convenience of using digital devices to keep children quiet, parental neglect, and excessive exposure to digital devices in the environment as the primary factors contributing to digital addiction.

Table 8.
Factors Leading to Digital Addiction

Theme	Participant Opinions	f
Parental neglect	P1, P2, P3, P5, P14, P19	6
Parental lack of knowledge	P1, P3, P5, P6, P7, P11, P13, P16, P19, P20	10
Increased use of digital devices in daily life	P1, P17, P18	3
Lack of quality time with family	P2, P13, P14	3
Parents as role models (excessive use)	P2, P3, P8, P9	4
Older siblings as role models	P8, P9	2
Parents working intensively	P3, P15, P19	3
Not removing devices from the home.	P3, P8	2
Children do not know how to spend their time	P4	1
Using phones to make children eat (wrong approach)	P6, P8, P20	3
Excessive exposure to devices in their surroundings	P7, P9, P10, P13, P17, P18	6
There are no time restrictions when using devices	P8, P14, P18	3
Allowing children uncontrolled use of devices	P14, P18	2
Lack of consistency	P8	1
Over-advertising of digital devices	P9	1
Ease of keeping children quiet with devices	P10, P11, P13, P14, P15, P16, P18	7
Children's interest in device content	P10, P15	2
Buying devices to make children happy	P12	1
Decline in street games	P15	1
Children feel lonely at home.	P20	1

The following responses that emerged from participants' responses vividly illustrate their thoughts.

P4: *Factors include children not knowing how to spend their time, lacking educational toys, and not attending social activities.*

P8: *Parents setting a poor example, ease of access to devices at home, and lack of consistency or time limits contribute to addiction.*

P13: *The root cause is the family. Inappropriate family structures and integrating digital devices into everyday life are key factors. Families lack awareness and education and fail to spend quality time with their children.*

P17: *Environmental and genetic factors, as well as psychological conditions like depression, can lead to digital addiction.*

Table 9.
Solutions to Eliminate Digital Addiction

Theme	Participant Opinions	f
Informing parents	P1, P2, P3, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, P17, P18, P19, P20	20
Informing school administrators	P2, P8, P9, P11, P13	5
Informing teachers	P2, P8, P9, P10, P11, P13, P16, P20	8
Informing children	P3, P5, P9, P12, P16, P17	6
Controlled use of digital devices (passwords)	P9, P18	2
Setting time limits	P1, P14, P15, P18	4
Teaching games and suggesting activities	P5	1
Informing caregivers (grandparents, babysitters)	P10, P11, P12, P14	4
Programs prepared by MoNE	P10, P14, P18, P19	4
Seeking expert support	P10, P13	2
Local authorities providing education	P17	1
Free training programs	P19	1
Activities for quality time	P19	1

Lastly, Table 9 clearly shows that all participants emphasize informing parents as the primary solution to combating digital addiction, followed by informing teachers, children, and school administrators.

P1: Parents should be trained on the importance of setting time limits.

P3: Parents must be educated about programs beneficial to children and the importance of controlling digital device use.

P10: Training programs should be developed by the Ministry of Education and experts for parents, caregivers, and teachers.

P13: Education should target families, teachers, and school administrators. Collaboration between families, teachers, and school management should be established with expert support.

P19: Parents, babysitters, and caregivers should be given free, local, or online education on digital addiction and its consequences. Training on spending quality time with children should also be provided.

4. Discussion

The findings of this study reveal the teachers' views on the effects of digital addiction on children in the preschool period. In the context of attention deficiency related to digital addiction in the preschool period, the study considers socio-demographic factors such as age, professional experience, institutions, job distribution, and whether they have received any training on digital addiction. Regarding the age variable, the participation of teachers between the ages of 25 and 55 in this research allows for understanding different generations' perspectives on how digital technologies have started to be integrated into education. Teachers from various age groups may contribute to the diversification of the research with their varying levels of awareness of digital addiction and attention deficiency. Many studies show that digital addiction affects not only children but also teachers. When Rosen et al. (2014) examined the effects of digital addiction on both adults and children, they noted that teachers' relationships with digital media model how students relate to digital media. Therefore, research involving teachers aged 25-55 can more clearly demonstrate how digital media usage habits reflect on the educational process. Based on educational level, the fact that most participants have a bachelor's degree suggests that the number of teachers who have received specific training on digital addiction and attention deficiency may be limited. However, it should also be considered that teachers with bachelor's degrees may possess in-depth knowledge of various pedagogical approaches and may have conducted significant research on preschool children.

Nevertheless, the limited number of specific training programs on digital addiction could reflect teachers' knowledge gaps. When Lemola et al. (2015) examined the relationship between digital media and child development, they stated that without proper training in digital media usage, teachers' awareness of the subject could be very low, potentially leading to adverse effects on children. This indicates that the level of education is a critical factor in teachers' ability to address digital addiction effectively. Teachers with 15-30 years of professional experience may have made significant observations regarding digital addiction and attention deficiency. These teachers may have had the opportunity to observe the integration of technology into teaching methods and its effects on children over many years. This highlights the importance of teachers' experience in addressing attention-deficiency issues related to digital addiction. While examining how digital media usage affects children's attention, memory, and learning processes, teachers who can make long-term observations have a significant advantage in recognizing the early signs of digital addiction. Teachers with extensive professional experience are better equipped to accurately assess changes in children's

development according to the characteristics of the institutions where they work and job distribution. The fact that most teachers work in public schools indicates that this research primarily addresses issues such as digital addiction and attention deficiency in preschool in public schools. Teachers in public schools generally serve students from more diverse socio-economic backgrounds. This can influence the diversification of awareness and intervention methods related to digital addiction. Przybylski and Weinstein (2013), in their study on the effects of digital media usage, emphasized the importance of raising awareness among teachers and parents to combat digital addiction. Such training allows teachers to develop healthier strategies by relating children's attention and focus skills to digital media usage.

The results show that digital devices negatively affect children's attention levels, particularly attention deficits and social skill deficiencies. Indeed, similar findings are consistent with previous research indicating that digital addiction in children can lead to issues such as attention deficit, social isolation, and aggression (Avcı & Er, 2019; Chassiakos et al., 2016; Gentile et al., 2014). Regarding digital addiction, teachers' views suggest that this addiction negatively affects children's social interactions and academic performance. Excessive attachment to digital devices leads to children ignoring the external world, negatively impacting their individual and social development. This finding aligns with the harmful effects of digital devices on social interaction and communication skills. In a similar study, Aksoy (2021) highlighted that some teachers believe digital devices can harm students' social and emotional development by examining the positive and negative aspects of these devices. According to Sönmezer and Balcıoğlu (2023), digitalization, in terms of encountering potentially harmful content, possesses positive and negative features, creating environments where children can experience psychological and physical harm. Therefore, children should be imbued with digital literacy and awareness from the beginning of their education to learn to responsibly use digital tools and online platforms (Arikan & Zorba, 2019).

5. Conclusions

The research ensured ethical considerations by providing participants with an informed consent letter that explained the study's purpose, ensured voluntary participation, and addressed anonymity and confidentiality. It is recommended to limit daily screen time to mitigate the adverse effects of digital device use on children's attention and social development (Hill et al., 2016). Raising parental awareness and educating them on strategies to manage digital exposure is crucial in preventing adverse impacts on children. Additionally, encouraging children to engage with educational and age-appropriate content during screen time can help maximize the benefits of digital devices. Promoting social activities and physical engagement, such as outdoor play and group interactions, fosters social skills and focus. For children showing signs of digital addiction, seeking professional support is advised to address and manage potential issues effectively.

Ethical Issues

The research ensured ethical considerations by providing participants with an informed consent letter that explained the study's purpose, ensured voluntary participation, and addressed anonymity and confidentiality—date of confirmation (11/01/2025).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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